

Acknowledgement

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Protein and Amino Acid Composition of Certain Plants of Cucurbitaceae

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A number of plants of the family cucurbitaceae grow in various parts of the country and possess several medicinal properties. The seeds of *Citrullus colocynthis* are used as nerve tonic¹. These plants grow abundantly in the Rajasthan desert. The seeds are rich in protein and possess all the essential amino acids except tryptophan². In the present investigation four plants of the family were examined.

The seeds were collected locally and identified systematically. The seedcoats were removed and the kernels defatted with petroleum ether b.p. (60-80°). The protein percentage was determined

* For correspondence.

by Modified Kjeldahl's method and also with spectrophotometric method³ which are in good agreement.

The defatted seed meal was extracted several times with 10% sodium chloride solution and the protein was precipitated with trichloroacetic acid. The precipitated protein was hydrolysed with 5.5 N HCl in sealed glass tubes. The acid free hydrolysate after repeated distillation *in vacuo* was subjected to paper chromatographic analysis. The amino acids were separated by two dimensional chromatography on Whatman No. 1 paper by butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5) and phenol : water (3 : 1) and were identified with spray reagents⁴⁻⁶.

Results and Discussion

The nitrogen and protein content of the seeds is given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Name of the plant	Weight of sample in g.	%N ₂	%protein
<i>Citrullus vulgaris</i>	0.1056	6.5	40.57
<i>Cucumms Melo</i>	0.0988	7.99	49.93
<i>Cucumms melo utilissimus</i>	0.1002	8.3	57.87
<i>Lagenaria vulgaris</i>	0.1002	7.15	44.68

Table 1 shows the nitrogen percentage as well as the protein percentage in the samples. It is interesting to note that all the plants analysed show high protein content. They also contain all the essential amino acids except Tryptophan. Looking at the high protein content these seeds can be suggested as cheap source of protein.

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